

On Graphical Partitions with Restricted Parts

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Abstract

We find the distributions of the parts of a random partition under general restrictions placed on them. We evaluate the fraction of the restricted partitions of an even integer n that are graphical. We find for which restrictions that are put on the parts this fraction is maximal, and show that in this case it is equal to $O(n^{-1/2})$. In addition, we prove that there exists a minimal lower bound for the parts of the partitions, for which the influence of the other restrictions on the fraction of graphical partitions becomes negligible, and this fraction is controlled only by the choice of the lower bound. For the case where all the parts are restricted to powers of 2, this critical lower bound is $\frac{1}{2}n^{\log 2} + O(\log n)$.

1 Introduction

A partition of an integer is called graphical if it is a degree sequence of a simple graph. Graphical partitions have been studied extensively, as well as partitions with restricted parts, such as parts that are bounded or of a certain form. However, to our knowledge, graphical partitions with general restrictions placed on their parts have not been enumerated, and the interactions between different restrictions acting on the parts simultaneously have not been investigated. For example, in this article we bring new insight on how different restrictions influence the fraction of partitions that are graphical, and study when the influence of one becomes more dominant than that of the other.

Graphical partitions have applications in combinatorics and network design, and studying how restrictions affect their behavior contributes to these and related areas, for instance, if one wants to construct a network under a set of given constraints.

Let $\mu(i)$ indicate the i -th smallest part a partition can have under the restrictions put on its parts. In Section 2 we show that $X_k, \mu(Y_k)$ have the same density distributions, where X_k is the number of parts that are $\geq k$ of a random restricted partition, and Y_k is the k -th largest part of this partition. Our result holds for general restrictions put on the parts of the partitions. In Section 3 we find a compact expression for the fraction of the restricted partitions of an even integer n that are graphical. Furthermore, we prove that for every restriction placed on the parts of the partitions, there exists a critical lower bound for

the parts, l_n , such that for any lower bound $l \geq l_n$, the fraction of graphical partitions of n becomes independent of the restriction, and is controlled only by the choice of l , and we evaluate, $l_n = \mu(\log n) - \log n$. In Section 4 we include concluding remarks.

2 Probability and partitions

In our work, we let $\mu : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a real function satisfying $\mu(n) \in \mathbb{N}$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, and represent by $\mu(\mathbb{N})$ the set of valid parts a partition may have under a chosen restriction. By choosing the function μ we may represent any restriction placed on the parts. Without loss of generality, we may focus only on functions μ that are odd, invertible and differentiable, satisfying $|\mu(x)| \geq |x|$ for all $x \in \mathbb{R}$. We may define M to be the set of all such functions.

Denote by \mathcal{P}_μ the set of all integer partitions with parts only from the set $\mu(\mathbb{N})$. Define a probability measure on \mathcal{P}_μ by, $\mathbb{P}_q(\lambda) = \frac{q^{|\lambda|}}{Z(q)}$, with $Z(q) = \sum_{\lambda \in \mathcal{P}_\mu} q^{|\lambda|}$, for all $\lambda \in \mathcal{P}_\mu$, and some $0 < q < 1$. Notice that this model fits the distribution of partitions of an integer n , since it becomes a uniform distribution when conditioned on the event $|\lambda| = n$:

$$\mathbb{P}_q(\lambda : |\lambda| = n) = \frac{q^n / Z(q)}{\mathbb{P}_q(|\lambda| = n)} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{P}_\mu(n)|}$$

where $\mathcal{P}_\mu(n)$ denotes the set of partitions of n from \mathcal{P}_μ .

Analogously to the work of Fristedt [4], we define $Z_m(\lambda)$ to be the number of parts equal to m in a partition $\lambda \in \mathcal{P}_\mu$. Since \mathbb{P}_q describes a Poisson process, we deduce $Z_m \sim \text{Geom}(q^m)$. Hence, $\mathbb{E}(Z_m) = \frac{q^m}{1 - q^m}$, and the condition $|\lambda| = n$ translates to:

$$n = \sum_{m \in \mu(\mathbb{N})} m \mathbb{E}(Z_m) = \sum_{m \in \mu(\mathbb{N})} \frac{mq^m}{1 - q^m}. \quad (1)$$

From equation (1) we may solve for $q(\mu, n)$. For the case $\mu(\mathbb{N}) = \mathbb{N}$, we may approximate the summation with an integral, yielding:

$$\sum_{m \in \mathbb{N}} \frac{mq^m}{1 - q^m} = \int_0^\infty \frac{u}{e^u - 1} du \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\log^2 q} + O(1) \right) = \frac{\pi^2}{6 \log^2 q} + O(1).$$

Then, we deduce $q = \exp(-\frac{\pi}{\sqrt{6n}})$. Notice that in this case, $\log q$ is just the radius of the contour in Szekeres circle method, he has used in [7] and [8]. Hence, we may denote $\alpha = -\log q$, for all $\mu \in M$, to match the notation of Szekeres.

For other choices of μ , the right-hand side of equation (1) decreases, then we conclude that for all $\mu \in M$ we have the following asymptotic inequality, $\alpha = -\log q \leq \frac{\pi}{\sqrt{6n}}$, where there is equality only for $\mu(\mathbb{N}) = \mathbb{N}$. There are more precise methods we could have used to evaluate α and q , but this upper bound will suffice for the purpose of this article. Notice that $\alpha \rightarrow 0$ in the limit $n \rightarrow \infty$, for all $\mu \in M$.

Now, let Y_1 be a random variable that is equal to the largest part in a partition of n from \mathcal{P}_μ . Then, its cumulative distribution function satisfies the following for all $y > 0$:

$$\begin{aligned} \log \mathbb{P}_q(Y_1 \leq y) &= \log \prod_{\substack{m \in \mu(\mathbb{N}) \\ m > y}} (1 - q^m) = - \sum_{\substack{m \in \mu(\mathbb{N}) \\ m > y}} e^{-\alpha m} (1 + O(e^{-2\alpha m})) \\ &= - \int_{\alpha y}^{\infty} e^{-x} d\mu^{-1}\left(\frac{x}{\alpha}\right) \cdot (1 + O(\alpha)) = - \frac{e^{-\alpha y}}{\alpha \mu'(\mu^{-1}(y))} (1 + O(\alpha)). \end{aligned}$$

Here, μ^{-1} is the inverse function of μ , which exists from the definition of the set M , as well as its derivative. We have also used, $\log(1 - x) = -x(1 + O(x))$. This result gives motivation to define a function $\eta : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ s.t. for constant α , it satisfies $\eta(y) = \alpha y + \log(\alpha \mu'(\mu^{-1}(y)))$, for all $y \in \mathbb{R}$. Then we have, $\log \mathbb{P}_q(Y_1 \leq y) = -e^{-\eta(y)}(1 + O(\alpha))$, which approaches the Gumbell distribution in the limit of large n . Hence, one can deduce from Gumbell order statistics that the k -th largest part in a random partition of n from \mathcal{P}_μ satisfies:

$$\mathbb{P}_q(\eta(Y_k) \leq y) \xrightarrow{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{(k-1)!} \int_{-\infty}^y e^{-e^{-u}} e^{-ku} du \quad (2)$$

for all $y > 0$ and $k \in \mathbb{N}$, analogous to the result of Fristedt.

We denote by a random variable X_k the number of parts greater than or equal to k in a partition of n from \mathcal{P}_μ . Fristedt showed that for the case $\mu(\mathbb{N}) = \mathbb{N}$, the variables X_k, Y_k have the same distributions for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$. In his derivation, Fristedt took advantage of the fact that the parts of a partition are the multiplicities of its conjugate partitions, and thus deduced equivalence between the distributions of X_k and Y_k . However, if a partition is from the set \mathcal{P}_μ , for some function $\mu \in M$, it is not necessarily true for its conjugate partition. Thus, the equivalence between partitions and their conjugates does not hold in general, when applying restrictions on their parts, so we must evaluate the distributions of X_k in another way.

Note that X_1 is the number of parts in the partition, we may deduce its distribution by evaluating the number of partitions from the set \mathcal{P}_μ of an integer $n \in \mathbb{N}$, which have at most $x \in \mathbb{N}$ parts; we may denote it by $|\mathcal{P}_\mu(n, x)|$. This can be done by using the theory of generating functions and the saddle-point method, one may check that:

$$|\mathcal{P}_\mu(n, x)| = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \oint_C z^{-n-1} \prod_{\substack{m \in \mu(\mathbb{N}) \\ m > \mu(x)}} \frac{1 - z^{m+\mu(x)}}{1 - z^m} dz.$$

Where C is a circular contour on the complex plane that centers at the origin and has a radius of $q = e^{-\alpha}$. This result resembles that of Szekeres and the derivation is almost the same, so we skip it. according to the saddle-point method, it is enough to evaluate the logarithm of the integrand and its derivative in order

to evaluate the integral. After substituting $z = e^{-\alpha+i\theta}$, we may denote the logarithm of the integrand by $G(\theta, n, x)$ and obtain the following:

$$G(\theta, n, x) = \alpha n - \sum_{\substack{m \in \mu(\mathbb{N}) \\ m > \mu(x)}} \log(1 - e^{-\alpha m}) + \sum_{\substack{m \in \mu(\mathbb{N}) \\ m > \mu(x)}} \log(1 - e^{-\alpha(m+\mu(x))}).$$

Each of these summations can be approximated by using the Taylor expansion of $\log(1-x)$, as we have already done above. For large x the second summation is negligible, then we may only approximate the first summation to obtain, $G(0, n, x) = -\frac{e^{-\alpha\mu(x)}}{\alpha\mu'(x)}(1 + O(\alpha))$. Here we have supposed that the number of partitions of n is dominated by large x , this is true for large enough n , s.t. a big fraction of its partitions have a large number of parts. It can be seen that the dependence of the derivatives $G'(0, n, x), G''(0, n, x)$ on x is negligible when x is large, then we find with a good approximation, $|\mathcal{P}_\mu(n, x)| \propto -\frac{e^{-\alpha\mu(x)}}{\alpha\mu'(x)}(1 + O(\alpha))$. We recall that x is the maximum number of parts in the partition, then $\mathbb{P}_q(X_1 \leq x) \propto |\mathcal{P}_\mu(n, x)|$, and thus we conclude that the variable $\eta \circ \mu^{-1}(X_1)$ has a Gumbell distribution, similar to that of $\eta(Y_1)$. So we also have for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$:

$$\mathbb{P}_q(\eta \circ \mu^{-1}(X_k) \leq x) \xrightarrow{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{(k-1)!} \int_{-\infty}^x e^{-e^{-u}} e^{-ku} du. \quad (3)$$

Hence, X_k, Y_k have different distributions when applying restrictions on the parts of the partitions for a fixed n . Since η is an invertible function we have:

Theorem 1 *Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\mu \in M$. For all $k \in \mathbb{N}$, denote by Y_k the k -th largest part of a partition of n from \mathcal{P}_μ and denote by X_k the number of parts greater than or equal to k . Then the density distributions of $X_k, \mu(Y_k)$ become equal in the limit $n \rightarrow \infty$, for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$:*

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\mathbb{P}_q(X_k = m)}{\mathbb{P}_q(\mu(Y_k) = m)} = 1, \quad \forall m, k \in \mathbb{N} \quad (4)$$

For example, when considering $\mu(\mathbb{N}) = \{2^{n-1} : n \in \mathbb{N}\}$, the set \mathcal{P}_μ is the set of all binary partitions. Then according to Theorem 1, for a large enough integer n , the variables $X_k, 2^{Y_k-1}$ have approximately the same distribution for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$, which means that the k -th largest part increases logarithmically to the number of parts $\geq k$.

3 Restricted Graphical Partitions

The first rank of a partition, first introduced by Dyson [2], is the difference between the largest part of the partition and the number of its parts. The k -th rank of a partition, as defined by Atkin [1], is the difference between the k -th largest part of the partition and the number of its parts that are greater than or equal to k . Then, if we denote it as a random variable R_k , we have $R_k = Y_k - X_k$. A partition is graphical if it is a degree sequence of a simple

graph. Nash-Williams [5] proved that if K is the Durfee square of a partition (the largest k s.t. $k \leq Y_k$) then the partition is graphical if and only if it sums up to an even integer and $\sum_{l=1}^k R_l \leq -k$, for all $k \leq K$. To our knowledge, graphical partitions with restricted parts have not been enumerated.

It is worthwhile to mention the result of Esseen's in Feller [3] Theorem 2, p. 554. Let A_k be independent variables such that:

$$\mathbb{E}(A_k) = 0, \quad \mathbb{E}(A_k^2) = \sigma_k^2, \quad \mathbb{E}(A_k^3) = \rho_k < \infty.$$

Set $s_n^2 = \sigma_1^2 + \sigma_2^2 \dots + \sigma_n^2$, and $r_n = \rho_1 + \rho_2 + \dots + \rho_n$. Let us also denote by F_n the density distribution of $s_n^{-1} \sum_{k=1}^n A_k$, then we have:

$$|F_n(x) - \mathbf{N}(x)| \leq 6 \frac{r_n}{s_n^3}. \quad (5)$$

Let $\mathcal{R}_k(r)$ be the density distribution function of R_k , for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$. Then, one can check that the following holds, from equations (2) and (3):

$$\mathcal{R}_k(r) = \frac{1}{(k-1)!2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-e^{-\eta^{-1}(r+x)} - e^{-\mu \circ \eta^{-1}(x)}} e^{-k(\eta^{-1}(r+x) + \mu \circ \eta^{-1}(x))} J(r, x) dx,$$

where $J(r, x) = \frac{d}{dx} \eta^{-1}(r+x) \frac{d}{dx} \mu(\eta^{-1}(x))$ is the Jacobian of the substitution $R_k = Y_k - X_k$. Then, by substituting $\eta^{-1}(r+x) \mapsto u$, we obtain the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[R_k] &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} r \mathcal{R}_k(r) dr \\ &= \frac{1}{(k-1)!2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx \left[e^{-e^{-\mu \circ \eta^{-1}(x)}} e^{-k\mu \circ \eta^{-1}(x)} \frac{d}{dx} \mu(\eta^{-1}(x)) \right. \\ &\quad \left. \times \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} du (\eta^{-1}(u) - x) e^{-e^{-u}} e^{-ku} \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{(k-1)!} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\mathbb{E}_k[\eta'] - \mu^{-1}(\eta(x)) \right) e^{-e^{-x}} e^{-kx} dx = \mathbb{E}_k[\eta^{-1}] - \mathbb{E}_k[\mu^{-1} \circ \eta]. \end{aligned}$$

Here, the notation $\mathbb{E}_k[f]$ denotes the mean of $f(X)$, where f is a real function and X is a random variable with a density distribution of $\frac{1}{(k-1)!} e^{-e^{-x}} e^{-kx}$.

In the same manner, one can check that:

$$\mathbb{E}[R_k^2] = \mathbb{E}_k[(\eta - \mu^{-1} \circ \eta)^2], \quad \mathbb{E}[R_k^3] = \mathbb{E}_k[(\eta - \mu^{-1} \circ \eta)^3]. \quad (6)$$

In order to apply Esseen's theory (5), we need to evaluate those mean values. Notice that all $\mu \in M$ satisfies $\mu(x) = O(x)$, hence, one may easily check that, $\log \mu'(\mu^{-1}(x)) = \Omega(\log x)$. Then, $\eta(x) = \alpha x + \log(\alpha \mu'(\mu^{-1}(x))) \approx \alpha x$, and thus, for sufficiently large x , $\eta^{-1}(x) \approx \alpha^{-1}x$. Hence, the parameter from equation (5) satisfies:

$$s_n^2 \approx \sum_{k=1}^n \alpha^2 \mathbb{E}_k[(x - \mu^{-1})^2] \approx n \alpha^2 \mathbb{E}_n[(x - \mu^{-1})^2],$$

In the same manner, we observe that $r_n \approx n \alpha^3 \mathbb{E}_n[(x - \mu^{-1})^3]$, thus we have:

Theorem 2 *Let $\mu \in M$. Then the fraction of partitions from \mathcal{P}_μ of an even integer n that are graphical is:*

$$O\left(\frac{\mathbb{E}_n[(x - \mu^{-1})^3]}{\mathbb{E}_n^{3/2}[(x - \mu^{-1})^2]}n^{-1/2}\right). \quad (7)$$

For example, we may restrict partitions to have only parts divisible by m , for some $m \in \mathbb{N}$, then let $\mu(x) = mx, \forall x \in \mathbb{R}$. So after evaluating the mean values, we deduce from Theorem 2 that the fraction of partitions with parts differentiable by m of an even integer n that are graphical is $O(n^{-1/2})$, in agreement with Rousseau and Ali [6]. Notice that the dependence on m vanished due to the division of the expected values. Hence, we have:

Theorem 3 *The fraction of graphical partitions of an even integer n decreases most slowly with n when the restriction put on the parts is linear, That is, the fraction is maximal when μ is linear. In that case, the fraction is $O(n^{-1/2})$.*

Furthermore, we notice that the fraction of graphical partitions is not sensitive to restrictions on small parts. For example, let $\mu \in M$ s.t. $\mu^{-1}(x) = x(1 - e^{-x/10})$ for all $x > 0$, then we have with a good approximation $\mu(x) \approx x$ for $x \geq 55$ (0.045% error). By evaluating numerically the expected values in expression (7), we verify that the fraction of graphical partitions out of \mathcal{P}_μ is $O(n^{-1/2})$, the same as if there were no restrictions at all. Thus, we deduce that most of the graphical partitions do not have any small parts, that is, parts smaller than 55. Notice that this result contradicts equation (4), since we have $X_k = n$ for all $k \leq 55$, but $\mu(Y_k) \approx Y_k$ cannot be equal to n , since it is only part of the partition. Hence, Theorem 1 does not apply after restricting the partitions to be graphical.

It is natural to question what the minimal lower bound that is needed to be put on the parts of the partitions from \mathcal{P}_μ such that the fraction of them being graphical is dominated by it, and the influence of the other restrictions becomes negligible.

In order to answer this query, we notice that the density distribution function $\frac{1}{(n-1)!}e^{-e^{-x}}e^{-nx}$ has a maximum at $x_{max} = -\log n$, and in the limit $n \rightarrow \infty$ it becomes the Dirac delta function centered at that point. Notice that applying a lower bound to the parts of the partitions is equivalent to shifting the function μ horizontally by this lower bound. We may evaluate this minimal lower bound, denoted by l_n , by setting the fraction of graphical partitions equal to zero, as an approximation. Then, according to that approximation, we have:

$$\mathbb{E}_n[(x - \mu^{-1}(x - l_n))^3] \approx (x - \mu^{-1}(x - l_n))^3 \Big|_{x=-\log n} = 0,$$

and thus,

$$l_n = \mu(\log n) - \log n. \quad (8)$$

This result holds up to an error that comes from the approximations mentioned above, and becomes more accurate as n is larger. Hence, we conclude:

Theorem 4 *Let $\mu \in M$ and let $n \in \mathbb{N}$ be an even integer. Then the minimal lower bound l_n needed to be put on the parts of the partitions from \mathcal{P}_μ , for which it dominates the asymptotic behavior of the fraction of graphical partitions is approximately:*

$$l_n = \mu(\log n) - \log n.$$

We get an elegant result when \mathcal{P}_μ is the set of all binary partitions, $\mu(n) = 2^{n-1}, \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$, in that case the minimal lower bound is:

$$l_n = \frac{n^{\log 2}}{2} + O(\log n).$$

4 Concluding Remarks

We have found a compact form for the proportion of the graphical partitions relative to the number of restricted partitions of an even integer, written in (7). However, this expression involves computing expected values, and it is worthwhile to ask for a more elegant closed form that still holds for general restrictions. Furthermore, we saw that there exists a critical value for the lower bound put on the parts, that beyond it the influence of the other restrictions on the fraction of graphical partitions becomes negligible. This is only one example of the interactions between restrictions placed on the parts of graphical partitions. It is worthwhile to investigate the interactions between other types of restrictions, and thus have a better understanding of the behavior of graphical partitions.

References

- [1] O. L. Atkin, *A note on ranks and conjugacy of partitions*, Quart. J. Math. Oxford Ser(2), 17 (1996), 335-338.
- [2] F. J. Dyson, *Some guesses in the theory of partitions*, Eurika (Cambridge), 8 (1944), 10-15.
- [3] W. Feller, *An Introduction to Probability Theory and Its Applications*, 2nd ed., J. Wiley and Sons, 1971.
- [4] B. Fristedt, *The structure of random partitions of large integers*, Trans. Amer. Math. Soc. 337 (1993), 703-735.
- [5] C. St. J. A. Nash-Williams: Valency sequences which force graphs to have Hamiltonian circuits; Interium Report C. and O. Research Report, Fac. of Math., U. of Waterloo.
- [6] C. Rousseau and F. Ali, *On a conjecture concerning graphical partitions*, Congr. Num. 104(1994), 150-160.

- [7] G. Szekeres, *An asymptotic formula in the theory of partitions, II*, Quart. J. Math. Oxford Ser. (2), 4.(1951), p. 96-111.
- [8] G. Szekeres, *Asymptotic distribution of the number and size of parts in unequal partitions*, Bull. Austral. Math. Soc., vol. 36 (1987) 89-97.